

Analysis of Cesarean Deliveries Using Robson's Ten Group Classification System between Secondary and Tertiary Healthcare Setting in Assam

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Abstract:

Introduction: The rising Cesarean section rate is a matter of global concern. In 1985, WHO recommended an optimal CS rate of 10-15%. Unless medically indicated, the true long- and short-term risks and benefits associated with the procedure are questionable. Hence, every case should be scrutinized.

Aims and Objective: To analyse and compare CS rates between a secondary and tertiary healthcare facility in Assam using the Robson classification system and subsequently suggest possible measures to address them.

Method: It is a descriptive study of 583 and 2939 cesarean deliveries conducted at a district hospital and Medical College in Assam respectively. The data was analyzed and compared using Robson's ten group classification system.

Results: The cesarean section rate at the district hospital was 22.17% and at AMCH it was 51.06%. In both settings, the top 3 contributors to the overall CS rate were group V, followed by group II and group I. However, the cases in subgroup IIA and IVA were nil in the district hospital. Group X contributed 9.62%, compared to 0.85% at district hospital.

Conclusion: Factors like patient profile, infrastructure, and facilities that influence the decision to perform cesarean sections vary in district hospital and medical college. Constant audits using Robson classification will help us target the main contributory groups and adjust institutional policies accordingly. Introducing labour induction and augmentation techniques in district hospital can reduce many avoidable CS. Reducing primary CS and encouraging VBAC will help reduce the overall CS rate.

Keywords: Cesarean Section Rate, Robson's Classification, secondary and tertiary centre.

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Introduction

Caesarean sections have become increasingly common in both developed and developing countries for a variety of reasons. [1] In 1985, WHO has considered an optimal rate of CS to be between 10% and 15% based on evidence available at that time. [2]. Caesarean sections can successfully reduce maternal and neonatal mortality and morbidity when medically indicated. Nonetheless, women and newborns may face additional short- and long-term health risks as a result of medically unnecessary caesarean surgery. [3]

Globally, the current CS rate is around 21%. These numbers have increased from just 7% in 1990 and are projected to increase to nearly one-third (29%) of all births by 2030. [4] In India, the proportion of cesarean deliveries has dramatically increased to 17% (2015-16) and 21.5% (2019-21) from just 3% in 1992-93. [5] According to the national representative survey, 1 in every 5 pregnant women

in India had a CS even if they did not require it medically. [6] Cesarean section rate in Assam also shows an increasing trend from 13.4% in 2015-2016 (NFHS-4) to 18.1% in 2019 – 2020 (NFHS-5). [7] Cesarean section rate varies widely among different institutions depending on the profile of obstetric populations they serve, socioeconomic factors, accessibility to existing healthcare, the capacity, provisions, and clinical management protocols. Therefore, a population-based recommended caesarean section rate cannot be applied as the ideal rate at the hospital level. Effective strategies to reduce the rate of caesarean sections in various obstetric units necessitate a careful analysis of each case to determine the patient groups undergoing the procedure most frequently. [8]

WHO in 2001, proposed Robson ten group classification system as a global standard for assessing, monitoring and comparing caesarean

section rates within and between healthcare facilities over time. The 10 groups are mutually exclusive and totally inclusive—i.e. all women can be classified, but each woman belongs to one and only one group. [2] In Assam there are very few studies comparing the Caesarean deliveries among different level of healthcare system. This study aimed to report and analyse CS rates between secondary and tertiary healthcare facility in Assam using the Robson classification system, and subsequently suggest possible measures to address them.

Materials and Method

This was a hospital-based retrospective observational study conducted at Assam Medical College and LGB Civil Hospital Tinsukia, Assam from 1/1/2023 to 31/7/23. Assam Medical College is a tertiary care center catering to a diverse population and is the main referral Centre for complicated cases from all the nearby primary and secondary level health care systems within and from neighboring states.

LGB Civil Hospital is a secondary care level hospital at Tinsukia district in Assam. It also serves as a referral unit for high-risk cases.

Data were collected from the records kept in the maternity ward, operation theatre and labour room. All relevant information like the total number of deliveries, including cesarean and vaginal deliveries conducted during the study period, was taken. Six parameters considered according to Robson's classification system were collected: obstetric history (parity, previous CS), onset of labour (spontaneous/induced/CS done before labour or during labour), fetal presentation (cephalic/ breech/ abnormal lie), number of fetuses, and gestational age (preterm/term). All the data were compiled and entered in a preformed structured proforma (Table 1).

Details were entered in Microsoft Excel Sheet and a total of 583 cesarean deliveries at civil hospital and 2939 CS done at AMCH in the study period were analyzed and compared.

Table 1: Robson's Ten Group Classification system

Robson's group	Characteristics
I	Nulliparous, single, cephalic, >37 weeks in spontaneous labor
IIA	Nulliparous, single cephalic, >37 weeks, induced labour
IIB	Nulliparous, single cephalic, >37 weeks, CS done before labor
III	Multiparous (excluding previous CS), single cephalic, >37 weeks in spontaneous labor
IVA	Multiparous (excluding previous CS), single cephalic, >37 weeks, induced labour
IVB	Multiparous (excluding previous CS), single cephalic, >37 weeks, CS before labor
V	Multiparous with previous CS, single cephalic, >37 weeks
VI	Nulliparous, single, breech pregnancy
VII	Multiparous, single, breech pregnancy, (including previous CS)
VIII	All women with multiple pregnancy, (including previous CS)
IX	All abnormal lies (including previous CS)
X	All single cephalic, <36 weeks (including previous CS)

Results

During the study period cases 2629 women delivered at LGB Civil Hospital, Tinsukia, 2046 were vaginal delivery (77.82%) and 583 cesarean sections (22.17%). Total of 5755 patients delivered at AMCH, out of which 2816 (48.93%) were vaginal

delivery and 2939 (51.06%) underwent caesarean section.

Total of 583 records from civil hospital and 2939 records from AMCH was analysed and incorporated in the study.

Table 2: Comparison of CS based on Robson's Ten Group Classification System for Assam Medical College and Hospital (AMCH) and LGB Civil Hospital, Tinsukia

AMCH			LGB CIVIL HOSPITAL, TINSUKIA	
Robson's Group	Number of CS	(%) Contribution made by each group to the overall CS	Number of CS	(%) Contribution made by each group to the overall CS
I	534	18.2%	99	16%
II	599	20.37%	149	25.5%
IIA	490	16.67%	0	0%
IIB	109	3.7%	149	25.5%
III	326	11.09%	54	9.2%
IV	311	10.53%	64	10.9%
IVA	210	7.10%	0	0%
IVB	101	3.43%	64	10.9%

V	641	21.8%	165	28%
VI	86	2.93%	15	2.5%
VII	76	2.58%	13	2.22%
VIII	55	1.87%	8	1.3%
IX	28	0.95%	6	1.02%
X	283	9.62%	5	0.85%

On comparing the data from both settings, Group V contributed the most (28% in district hospital and 21.8% in AMCH).

Secondly, Group 2 contributed 25.5% to the district hospital and 20.37% to the overall CS rate in AMCH. However, no cases were assigned to subgroup IIA in the district hospital as labour induction techniques were not practiced. Only in 3.7% of cases (group IIB), prelabour CS was done at AMCH, compared to 25.5% at district hospital. The same reason is being attributed to group IVB, which constitutes 10.9% in the district hospital as compared to 3.4% at AMCH. Targeting these two groups would help in reducing CS rate at district level.

The third important was group 1, contributing 16% in civil and 18% in AMCH. Percentage-wise group 5 and 2 together contributed to more than half of the total cesarean sections (53.5%) conducted at the district hospital. The Caesarean rates in the other groups between the two settings were almost similar; except for group X. Group X contributed 0.85% to the overall CS rate in district hospital compared to 9.62% at AMCH.

Discussion

One important technique to reduce morbidity and mortality among mothers and newborns is caesarean delivery. It is also one of the best indicators of the quality of maternal health services. [9]

The Cesarean Section rate in our study was 22.17% in civil hospital and 51% in AMCH. Overall prevalence of CS according to NFHS5 was 21.50% in India and 18.1% in Assam. [7] It is higher than the 10-15% rate recommended by WHO. Maurya et al, 2021 found caesarean section rate of 27.3% in a study conducted at district hospital in west Bengal. [10] In the systematic review of 21 articles on same topic from 2018 onwards by Jiandani F et al, they documented a minimal CS rate of 16.2% by Liane et al, 2023 while Naik et al.'s study in 2021 revealed the greatest CS rate of 61.2%. [11] The fact that AMCH is the only tertiary care hospital in this region and majority of the cases referred to here are high-risk cases is likely one of the causes of the hospital's high caesarean rate.

In our study in both the settings top three contributors to the overall CS rate was group V followed by group 2 and group 1. These findings

were similar to various studies done at tertiary centres in different parts of north and south India. [12,13,14]. Studies performed in Australia, Canada, and Brazil reported similar outcomes. [15,16,17] Parveen et al. reported group X as the highest (50.9%) contributor followed by group V (14.4%) and group I (11.4%). [18] Pravina et al. have reported group V as the leading cause (34.97%), followed by group I (26.35%) contributing to total CS. [14] The disparity in contributions of different group from various institutions illustrates the value of Robson's classification, which aids in the creation of centre-specific plans and objectives related to certain TGCS subgroups to reduce the rising CS rate.

On comparing the data of both settings in our study, Group V (post CS, single, cephalic term pregnancy) contributed the most (28% in civil hospital and 21.8% in AMCH). In the district hospital there was a lack of provision for planned VBAC and adequate number of staff for proper monitoring and management of any untoward events of such patients undergoing labour. Hence, for post CS cases, either elective or emergency CS were done, and all the high-risk cases were referred to a higher centre. Also, there was a lack of adequate information about the previous CS and the dilemma of scar integrity hindered VBAC in many cases. Majority of them opted for tubectomy and that was also one of the reasons to avoid the risk of VBAC in both settings.

Secondly, Group 2 contributed 25.5% in civil and 20.37% in AMCH. However, the important difference was there were no patients in group IIA (nulliparous, single cephalic, >37 weeks, induced labour) in civil hospital. Labour induction techniques were not practised at district hospital, reason being lack of adequate staffs for monitoring purpose. In AMCH 16.67% CS were contributed by nulliparous term single cephalic pregnancy with induced labour. CS was done for this group in cases of failed induction or any maternal or fetal distress. Only in 3.7% cases prelabour CS was done.

At district hospital pre labour CS was commonly done for cases like post-dated pregnancy, hypertensive disorders, gestational diabetes, slow progress of labour, fear of litigation issues or at maternal requests etc. Same reason being attributed for group IVB which constitute 10.9% in civil hospital as compared to 3.4% at AMCH. Targeting these two groups would help the efforts in reducing

CS rate. Also, whether the fair trial of induction was given or not needs to be evaluated to reduce CS rate due to failed induction at tertiary centre.

The third important group was group 1 (nulliparous, single, cephalic, >37 weeks in spontaneous labour), contributing 16% in civil and 18% in AMCH. Avoidance of primary CS by proper analysis of indication, proper patient selection for labour induction, labour augmentation techniques, proper counselling, and labour analgesia may reduce the rate of CS to a large extent. Malpresentation, fetal distress, cord prolapses, placenta previa, uterine rupture, failed labour induction, macrosomia, preeclampsia, and prior caesarean sections are common medical grounds for a caesarean section. Some of these indicators are subjective and changeable for decision-makers (physicians, healthcare professionals, including midwives) in the absence of guidelines with clear standards. [19]

In our study at LGB Civil Hospital, group V, II, I, and III made the highest percentage of CS (78.7%). In AMC, group V, II, I, and III collectively contributed 71.5% of the total CS.

According to a study by Hota et al. (2023), 88.16% of the total CS was contributed by the top four groups (X, V, II, and I) [20]. Group X's share of the total CS rate at AMCH was 9.62%, compared to only 0.85% at civil hospital. The obvious reason being availability of better NICU facilities and higher number of complicated cases like IUGR, preeclampsia, APH being referred here which warrants preterm deliveries. Indication for CS depends on clinical conditions as well as institutional protocol and patient's opinion after counselling. Low-risk individuals in the Robson 1 and 2 categories should be given priority with reasonable goals in both the settings to reduce the overall CS rate.

Limitation: Duration of the study period was 7 months only. Data was collected retrospectively so the relative size of each group could not be calculated due to lack of complete information. The detailed analysis on indications for CS among the subgroups would have been possible if it was a longitudinal study. Also, the rate of CS in this institution might not be the true reflection of the overall rate in the district and state. More research and timely audit should be done to understand the various factors influencing CS rate at different level of health system to bring changes to reduce the overall rate.

Conclusion

In order to identify potential areas for improvement and ultimately reduce total CS rates, it is critical to continuously assess CS rates over time and compare them with past data. Robson's ten-group

classification system may be considered to be the primary step in this effort in all the setups. Proper counseling, pain management, labour induction techniques especially in secondary care hospitals, training of staffs, augmentation of labour using oxytocin drips and VBAC should be encouraged. Proper documentation of OT findings on discharge sheet can help the staffs get a rough idea of previous CS during present delivery and accordingly plan for VBAC. Efforts to reduce the overall CS rate should focus on reducing the primary CS rates. Constant audits of CSs being performed are necessary as each hospital caters different group of population. Analyzing this trend in different settings and resulting potential reasons for these, can help in refining the hospital protocols from time to time and also benefit the state and country in policymaking. Henceforth reduces unnecessary strain on existing and already limited resources without compromising the healthcare needs of those who actually need them.

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